

MICROSTRUCTURE/FRACTURE PROPERTY RELATIONSHIPS OF LIQUID CRYSTAL POLYMER COMPOSITES*

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ABSTRACT

Notched Instrumented Izod (NII) and Modular Falling Weight (MFW) impact tests on an LCP matrix and its short glass-fiber reinforced composites were performed in this work. The analysis of the microstructure of the matrix and microstructural failure mechanisms were carried out by SEM. The high anisotropy in mechanical properties of the neat resin is remarkable. This anisotropy is reduced by increasing the thickness of the plate as well as by adding fibers to the matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Thermotropic liquid crystal polymers (LCP) are a relatively new class of polymers which combine the advantage of easy processability by methods common for thermoplastic polymers with unique mechanical properties and excellent chemical resistance. Therefore the interest in LCP is growing rapidly. As a result of highly oriented polymer chains a distinct structure and an anisotropic mechanical behavior with highest values of both strength and elastic modulus parallel to the flow direction can be obtained.

In this study the work was focused on the investigation of the microstructure and impact behavior of an LCP system and of its short glass-fiber reinforced composites. In particular, it was of special interest how the thickness of the materials and the fiber fraction influence their impact properties.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

MATERIALS

The polymer investigated is a wholly aromatic polyester (liquid crystal polymer LCP produced by Du Pont, Wilmington, Delaware, USA). Besides the neat resin, two kinds of short glass fiber (GF) filled composites with 30wt% and 50wt% GF respectively were also employed. All materials were in the form of injection-molded, end-gated, square plaques with 12.7cm in both width and length. The thickness of the plates ranged from 0.8mm to 3.2mm for the pure matrix and, 3.2 cm for the composites. The material codes and some other information are shown in TABLE 1.

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TABLE 1 Specimen Codes and Physical Data

Specimen Code	Plaque Thickness (B)		Glass Fiber Content	
	(mm)	(inch)	wt%	vol%
TYPE A	0.8	1/32	--	--
TYPE B	1.6	1/16	--	--
TYPE C	3.2	1/8	--	--
TYPE D	3.2	1/8	30	17.8
TYPE E	3.2	1/8	50	33.6

MICROSCOPY

The microscopic work was done with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Specimens used for determining the orientation distribution of the short fibers and the thickness of microlayers were polished with alumina and diamond powder. Prior to the SEM studies the polished specimens as well as fracture surfaces of specimens used in the mechanical tests were sputter-coated with gold.

MECHANICAL TESTING

NOTCHED IZOD IMPACT TESTS

An impact pendulum connected with a fractoscope data acquisition unit

Fig. 1 Schematic picture of the definition of F_{max} and E_{max} measured in NII and MFW tests

type ceast AFS-MK3 and an HP computer were used to determine the impact performance of razor Notched Izod Impact (NII) test samples (impact velocity = 3.46 m/sec, pendulum mass = 1.25 kg). Their initial notch ran either in L or in T direction (T means the direction of the crack is perpendicular to the mold fill direction (MFD) and L means this direction is parallel to MFD). A typical force-displacement curve recorded during one of the tests is shown in Fig. 1. The load to the maximum peak (F_{max}) and the energy to this maximum peak (E_{max}) could be determined.

INSTRUMENTED MODULAR FALLING WEIGHT TESTS

MFW tests were also performed at room temperature (the same data collecting unit as in NII test was used). The rectangular plates with 50 mm x 50 mm in size were impacted by a metallic striker (tip radius 20 mm, impact velocity = 6.26 m/sec, impact mass = 12 kg).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MICROSTRUCTURAL DETAILS

In agreement with previous reports [1-6], the thickness (B) of both the matrix plates and the composites consists of approximately three layers,

Fig. 2 Photograph taken from a polished cross-section of neat matrix plate shows that the thickness of the material consists of three layers.

Fig. 3 C/B ratio vs thickness of the specimen

two skin-layers (S) and a core-layer (C) (Fig.2). The C/B ratios varied with thickness B and volume fraction of the fibers. When the material plate was thicker and the fiber fraction was higher, the C/B ratio became larger (Fig. 3).

In the neat matrices, the skin-layers consisted of a set of different microlayers which had fibrous connections among them (Fig.4). Parabolic flow lines were visible in the core layer (Fig. 5). The molecular orientation in the skin layers was predominantly parallel to the MFD, whereas the opposite was true in the core layer (Fig.6).

The short fibers in the composites exhibited an orientation distribution well-known for injection-molded short-fiber reinforced thermoplastics [7-9]. They had a preferred orientation which was parallel to MFD in the two skin-layers and perpendicular to the MFD in the core-layer.

The bonding between the matrix and fibers seemed to be very poor. During the tests the fibers were pulled out over a length of several hundred micrometers, and there was almost no matrix adhering to them (Fig. 7).

Fig. 4 A TEM photograph of a specimen cut from the skin-layer of matrix shows that the polymer consists of microlayers and is fibrillar in nature in the surface region.

Fig. 5 SEM photograph taken from a fracture surface of neat matrix L-cracked specimen illustrated that in the skin-layers the molecular orientation is parallel to mold filling direction (MFD), but it is not true in the core-layer.

Fig. 7 A SEM photograph taken from the fracture surface of the material with 17.8 vol% GF) in core-layer. Fiber pull-out is clear and the ends of the fiber are pretty long.

Fig. 6 Transmitted electron micrographs, (a) specimen cut from core layer, showing a diffraction pattern with the beam parallel to the MFD, the orientation perpendicular to the MFD is visible. The opposite is true for the specimen cut from skin-layer (b).

MECHANICAL TEST RESULTS

NOTCHED IZOD IMPACT TESTS (NII)

The Fracture energy data achieved in the NII test are shown in Fig.8. For the LCP matrix the high anisotropy in the mechanical behaviour is very clear. For instance, the maximum energy (W_{max}) to break a neat LCP specimen at a thickness of 0.8 mm with a notch in T-direction is almost 3.59 times larger than that to break an L-notched specimen. The high anisotropy can also be illustrated by the macroscopic view of the fractured specimens (Fig. 9). The L-cracked specimen has a quite smooth fracture surface, and a much more complex fracture mode is found with the T-cracked specimens. It is obvious that delamination occurred during the procedure of T-crack propagation. A comparison of the results

obtained from the neat LCP matrix with those of the short fiber reinforced composites, yields the following information:

- 1) W_{max} values of both the T- and L-notched specimens are slightly increasing with fiber content (thickness 3.2 mm in both cases).
- 2) The degree of anisotropy is reduced by adding fiber into matrix.
- 3) The effect of plaque thickness on W_{max} of the matrix is more pronounced in the T-samples than in the L-cracked specimens. This indicates that the skin layers determine much more effectively the property profile of the material than the core region.

Fig. 8 W_{max} -B and W_{max} - V_f curves obtained in NII tests.

Fig. 9 Comparison of the fracture patterns of the L- (down) and T-cracked (up) specimens in the NII test for LCP matrix.

MODULAR FALLING WEIGHT TESTS (MFW)

For the MFW tests the influence of the thickness of the plates on the normalized values of W_{max} (normalized by relating the absolute values of load and energy to the plate thickness B and the diameter of the striker D , i.e. $\pi \cdot D \cdot B$) is shown on Fig. 10. The thinnest plaques require the highest specific values of both load and energy to punch a hole. Between the two thicker plaque geometries, no clear trends could be generated within the limited number of tests carried out here. But one thing is quite certain that the addition of fibers into the LCP matrix improved W_{max} clearly.

The anisotropic behaviour of the materials is also proved when studying the holes generated during the test (Fig.11). Cracks caused by the impact striker in the unfilled matrix tend to run along the direction which is parallel to the MFD, i.e. the orientation of the molecules in the skin layers. A high degree of delamination between microlayers over the plaque thickness is also noticeable.

Fig. 10 W_{max} - B and W_{max} - V_f curves obtained from the MFW tests.

Fig. 11 A Photograph of an impacted MFW specimen, the influence from the orientation of fibers and molecules is clear. The cracks generated during the impact procedure tends to run along the lines parallel to the molecular and/or fiber orientation.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS ON THESE RESULTS

- 1) Testing of specimens with preferred molecular and/or fiber orientation parallel to the loading direction (T-sample, cracks transverses to this direction) resulted in clearly higher values than in the opposite case (L-specimen). This is a clear evidence for the high anisotropy of the LCP-materials under consideration here.
- 2) The anisotropy of the materials' properties was highest for the thinnest LCP samples, because they possess an almost uniform molecular orientation parallel to the mold filling direction over the complete cross section. Increasing the plaque thickness increases the core region of different molecular orientation than in the skin layers, which results in a reduction of impact strength in T-direction and a slight increase in L-direction.
- 3) Adding glass fibers to the LCP-matrix increases maximum impact loads in both directions, whereas the trends in the absorbed energies to fracture are different between the NII- and the MFD-tests.

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